

STUDY OF THE INFLUENCE OF SURFACE CONTAMINATION ON THE ELECTRICAL PARAMETERS OF A PHOTOELECTRIC BATTERY IN KUMKURGAN CONDITIONS

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Abstract. *This study investigated the impact of surface contamination on a silicon photovoltaic (PV) cell over a one-month period. Changes in short-circuit currents of two identical solar panels were analyzed under the influence of both daytime and nighttime pollution in Kumkurgan conditions. The severity of PV surface pollution on days with strong winds was determined, leading to significant scientific and practical conclusions.*

Keywords: *photovoltaic battery, short-circuit current, dust level, Zenith, radiation intensity.*

Introduction

Wind erosion is a major concern in Uzbekistan, particularly affecting on Kashkadarya, southeastern Surkhandarya, and western Fergana regions [1]. The primary cause of dust formation in the air due to wind erosion is the arid climate. The dry Aral Sea, along with the accumulation of salt lakes and salt marshes in the republic, contribute to the release of dust and salt particles into the atmosphere. Observations which carried out in the recent years indicate a significant increase in dust density in Uzbekistan. Sand winds are prevalent in the central and southwestern districts of the republic during summer and the dusty season. Under the influence of these winds, saline soil particles settle on PV surfaces, forming a layer that increases over time [2]. While the concentration of dust in the air in mountain and sub-mountain regions of Uzbekistan is insignificant during winter and early spring, allowing rain and snow to cleanse the PV surfaces and increase the coefficient of useful work by 8-15% [3], this situation changes drastically in the second half of May. From May onwards, the concentration of dust increases sharply and persists until the end of November. In Tashkent (geographical latitude $\sim 40^{\circ}$), the decrease in PV parameters per month can be as high as 25-35%, reaching 40% from June to October. In Termez, the minimum decrease is 45%, with a maximum of 77% [4]. During the summer and autumn months, the increase in dust concentration is exacerbated not only by winds originating from the Aral Sea and salt lakes but also by agricultural activities that begin in spring and continue until late autumn. Consequently, the PV surface requires more frequent cleaning during these periods compared to late autumn or winter.

The severity of pollution is most pronounced when PV panels are horizontally positioned. Over time, the interaction of atmospheric precipitation with the glass can lead to damage, specifically glass corrosion. This corrosion occurs due to a chemical reaction between Na^+ ions and hydroxyl groups (OH^-) in the surface layer [5]. The degradation of the PV surface can extend up to a few micrometers, resulting in opacity. The corroded glass layer can exhibit rough mechanical stresses, damage such as cracks and scratches, and altered physical properties, including a lower refractive index and coefficient of thermal expansion. When the glass surface is

well-wetted with water, the water film can persist for a considerable time, even if the glass is installed vertically. After the water dries, traces remain. This type of pollution, where water plays a significant role, is termed "wet pollution" [6]. In contrast, "dry pollution" occurs when various substances from the environment settle evenly on the outer surfaces of the glass without water wetting. In the absence of water wetting, various substances from the environment usually settle evenly on the outer surfaces of the glass. This pollution is called dry pollution.

Dust particles in the atmosphere are very large. Their diameter ranges from about 1 nm to several tens of microns, and there are particles consisting of several molecules (clusters). The degree of deposition of various particles in PV depends on their size [7]:

- large particles - more than 100 microns, fall with a speed of about 0.5 m/s;
- average particles - from 1 to 100 microns, sink slowly with a speed of about 0.2 m/s;
- small particles - less than 1 micron, falling very slowly, in a calm atmosphere this process can last from several days to several years. In a windy atmosphere, they never sink, they can be washed away by rain.

In [8], the dependence of the air speed cleaning the PV surface on the distance to the PV surface was studied. It has been shown that low air velocities are required to remove large particles with a small electric charge. It became clear that the main pollution factor for the PV surface is particles with a small diameter [9].

Methods and materials

The research device utilizes a photovoltaic (PV) module composed of monocrystalline silicon solar cells. The PV module contains 36 solar cells and has a power output of 15W under AM 1.5 conditions.

We investigated the degree of PV surface pollution during daylight hours. The climate in Kumkurgan is characterized by a dry environment with a nearly twofold difference in night and day temperatures during the spring and summer seasons. Practically, if we assume that a range of particles of different sizes are transported by wind during the day due to solar energy absorption, dust deposition primarily occurs at night. To test this assumption, two PV modules were selected, exhibiting nearly identical short-circuit current and short-circuit voltage values (within 1%). The experiment was conducted in an open field in Kumkurgan district. Figure 1 shows the PVs installed for the experiment.

To maximize pollution of the PVs, they were positioned horizontally. The first PV module's surface was covered during the day and exposed at night (from 7:00 p.m. to sunrise, until 7:00 a.m.). The second PV module, unlike the first, remained uncovered throughout the day.

PV parameters were measured daily at the sun's zenith point. This ensured maximum solar radiation falling on the PV surface, minimizing measurement errors.

In the experiment, short-circuit current of PV, intensity of solar radiation, air temperature were measured.

Results and Discussion

The degree of pollution of the PV surface was determined according to the following formula:

$$\gamma = \frac{I_0 - I_n}{I_0} \cdot 100\% \quad (1)$$

where, γ – the level of pollution;

I_0 – the initial value of the short-circuit current, that is, before pollution;

I_n – the value of the short-circuit current after n days.

Figure 1. Installation of PVs for the experiment.

- 1 – cover;**
- 2 – PV whose surface opens only at night;**
- 3 – PV whose surface is always open;**
- 4 – base structure with two-axis rotation relative to the sun;**
- 5 – multimeter;**
- 6 – pyronometer;**
- 7 – thermometer.**

Figure 2. Irradiance intensity and short-circuit currents of PVs in July and August 2024.

In figure (1), the values of short-circuit currents before and after contamination are obtained, indicating that dust adhering to the PV surface affects its short-circuit current. Consequently, PV efficiency decreases. Figure 2 shows the radiation intensity and short-circuit currents of the PVs at the time of the sun's zenith for a month.

Figure 3 presents the time (day) dependence of the two PV pollution levels from the study conducted in July and August 2024. As the graphs illustrate, for July, both PV pollution levels, as a function of the number of days, reach saturation as the pollution thickness increases.

Figure 3 shows the results of the PV surface pollution survey conducted during July and August 2024. Importantly, these measurements were made without considering changes in wind speed. Surface pollution levels for the two PVs were nearly identical up to July 11th. However, a strong wind blowing from the south of the republic, with speeds ranging from 7-8 m/s to 15-16

m/s, persisted from the evening of July 29th to the evening of July 30th. This increase in wind speed led to a 15% increase in the difference in pollution levels between the two PVs.

Figure 3. Time dependence of surface pollution levels in July and August 2024.

In general, contamination levels for PVs with exposed surfaces during the studies are moderate, 25%, and for PV, whose surface opens only at night, it was ~15%.

Figure 4. Microscopic images of the surface of PVs.

(a) before contamination, (b) after 30 days of PV with surface exposed only at night, (c) PV after 30 days with the surface always open.

Figure 4 shows microcosmic images of dust particles in PV captured using a Digital Microscope 1000X, 8 LEDs, USB 2.0 digital microscope.

Conclusion

Covering the PV surface with a special cover at night and opening it before sunrise, while also adjusting its installation based on the PV's latitude, can significantly reduce surface pollution. Implementing this approach in photovoltaic plants could lead to higher efficiency. This is particularly relevant if PVs can be remotely controlled using a dedicated automated system that operates based on sunset and sunrise time intervals. To draw more accurate conclusions about reducing the impact of pollution on PV parameters, similar studies should be conducted in all regions of the republic.

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